

Coral Holobiont Amplicon Library Preparation for Illumina Sequencing: Bacterial 16S, Symbiodiniaceae ITS2, and Coral ITS2

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Summary

Amplicon sequencing provides a cost-effective and scalable approach to profile key biological compartments of the coral holobiont, including bacterial communities, Symbiodiniaceae algal symbionts, and the coral host. This protocol describes library preparation for three complementary marker systems: bacterial 16S rRNA gene amplicons, Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 amplicons, and coral ITS2 amplicons for paired-end Illumina sequencing. The workflow is intended for coral tissue DNA and supports applications such as coral microbiome surveys, Symbiodiniaceae community profiling, host species confirmation where suitable ITS2 reference data are available. The protocol is modular and can be applied to individual marker systems or combined to generate multi-compartment coral holobiont profiles from the same sample set.

Objective

To provide a standardized and modular workflow for preparing barcoded bacterial 16S, Symbiodiniaceae ITS2, and coral ITS2 amplicon libraries from coral DNA samples for paired-end Illumina sequencing. The protocol aims to support reproducible sample amplification, unambiguous sample identification through dual-barcoding, bead-based cleanup and normalization, pooling, and final pooled amplicon preparation for sequencing library generation.

Keywords: amplicon sequencing, coral holobiont, coral metaorganism, Symbiodiniaceae, Microbiome, ITS2, 16S

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Sample-barcoding PCR protocol - Bacterial 16S rRNA gene amplicon survey

Objective: Barcoded primers and PCR amplification conditions for DNA extracted from coral samples. Samples will be individually amplified and then pooled prior to sequencing submission.

- use your DNA extraction method of choice

Note: We typically use the Qiagen DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (69504) because it generally yields DNA of suitable quantity and quality for coral amplicon sequencing [1]. However, recent experimental data suggest that this kit may preferentially recover coral host DNA relative to Symbiodiniaceae and bacterial DNA (data in preparation). While this may be acceptable for comparative analyses across samples processed with the same extraction method, it may affect estimates of bacterial and Symbiodiniaceae diversity and relative abundance. For bacterial 16S and Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 amplicon surveys, we therefore recommend considering DNA isolation protocols with more balanced recovery across holobiont compartments, such as the Qiagen DNeasy Plant Pro Kit (69204). For multi-marker profiling, the same DNA extracts should be used across all amplicon assays to maintain comparability.

- use your 16S amplicon primers of choice

Note: Despite prevalence/popularity of the 16S V4 region, we noted amplification problems with coral samples; we also noted sizeable amplification of the chloroplast 12S DNA region using these primers; for this reason, we still advocate use of 16S V5-V6 [2], which generates a 280 bp amplicon; details on primer testing can be found in a previous study [3].

Forward primer (784F): 5'- AGG ATT AGA TAC CCT GGT A -3'

Reverse primer (1061R): 5'- CRR CAC GAG CTG ACG AC -3'

- primer barcoding

Note: We use 8 barcoded forward primers and 12 barcoded reverse primers, generating 96 unique forward/reverse barcode combinations for unambiguous sample identification. Primer details and the 96-well plate layout are provided below.

Name	Sequence (5'-3'; barcode in bold)
16S 784F 1	AACGTG ATAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 2	AAACATCG AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 3	CATCAAGT AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 4	CGCTGATC AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 5	ACGTATCA AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 6	ACTATGCA AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 7	CAGCGTTA AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 784F 8	CATACCAA AGGATTAGATACCCTGGTA
16S 1061R 1	GCTAACGAC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 2	GCTCGGTAC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 3	TATCAGCAC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 4	TCCGTCTAC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 5	AATGTTGCC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 6	ACACGACCC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 7	GATGAATCC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC
16S 1061R 8	GCCAAGACC RRCACGAGCTGACGAC

16S 1061R 9 **TGGTGGTACRRCACGAGCTGACGAC**
 16S 1061R 10 **TTCACGCACRRCACGAGCTGACGAC**
 16S 1061R 11 **CGACTGGACRRCACGAGCTGACGAC**
 16S 1061R 12 **CGCATACACRRCACGAGCTGACGAC**

		R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
F1	A	F1 + R1	F1 + R2	F1 + R3	F1 + R4	F1 + R5	F1 + R6	F1 + R7	F1 + R8	F1 + R9	F1 + R10	F1 + R11	F1 + R12
F2	B	F2 + R1	F2 + R2	F2 + R3	F2 + R4	F2 + R5	F2 + R6	F2 + R7	F2 + R8	F2 + R9	F2 + R10	F2 + R11	F2 + R12
F3	C	F3 + R1	F3 + R2	F3 + R3	F3 + R4	F3 + R5	F3 + R6	F3 + R7	F3 + R8	F3 + R9	F3 + R10	F3 + R11	F3 + R12
F4	D	F4 + R1	F4 + R2	F4 + R3	F4 + R4	F4 + R5	F4 + R6	F4 + R7	F4 + R8	F4 + R9	F4 + R10	F4 + R11	F4 + R12
F5	E	F5 + R1	F5 + R2	F5 + R3	F5 + R4	F5 + R5	F5 + R6	F5 + R7	F5 + R8	F5 + R9	F5 + R10	F5 + R11	F5 + R12
F6	F	F6 + R1	F6 + R2	F6 + R3	F6 + R4	F6 + R5	F6 + R6	F6 + R7	F6 + R8	F6 + R9	F6 + R10	F6 + R11	F6 + R12
F7	G	F7 + R1	F7 + R2	F7 + R3	F7 + R4	F7 + R5	F7 + R6	F7 + R7	F7 + R8	F7 + R9	F7 + R10	F7 + R11	F7 + R12
F8	H	F8 + R1	F8 + R2	F8 + R3	F8 + R4	F8 + R5	F8 + R6	F8 + R7	F8 + R8	F8 + R9	F8 + R10	F8 + R11	F8 + R12

- perform 1 PCR per sample with 5-20 ng DNA input (works with as little as 1-2 ng DNA input)

Note: We commonly use 1 μ L of the extracted DNA; in our experience, less DNA works better as you also increase the amount of putative inhibitors with higher DNA amounts (i.e., sample volumes); consider using a DNA cleanup kit if amplification is an issue.

- Prepare the master mix according to the number of samples. Include a 5–10% excess volume to account for pipetting loss (prepare 100–105 reactions for 96-well plate).

Reagent	1 reaction [μ L] / per well
Qiagen Multiplex PCR master mix (Qmix)	5
Nuclease free water	3
MasterMix volume	8
Forward & Reverse Primer [10 μ M]; sample-specific	1
DNA template; sample-specific	1
Total volume (PCR reaction)	10

PCR thermocycler program:

95°C 15 mins (hot start)
 95° C 30 secs |
 55°C 30 secs | 30 cycles
 72°C 30 secs |
 72°C 10 mins
 hold at 12°C

Note: We commonly aim to use 30 PCR cycles as a trade-off between sufficient amplification and preservation of relative abundance information. Increasing the number of cycles may improve product yield, but can also increase PCR bias and distort relative abundance ratios; use 35 cycles in case of weak PCR amplification

Note: We commonly use a hold temperature of 12°C; 4°C is shortens the lifetime of thermal cyclers and costs excessive energy

- Confirm successful PCR amplification by running 2 μ L PCR product (+2 μ L water + 1 μ L 6X loading dye) on a gel

Note: Check for distinct, sharp bands; commonly, band intensity varies across samples; always run a 1kb ladder and ideally positive/negative PCR control

Sample-barcoding PCR protocol - Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 amplicon survey

Objective: Barcoded primers and PCR amplification conditions for DNA extracted from coral samples. Samples will be individually amplified and then pooled prior to sequencing submission.

- use your DNA extraction method of choice

Note: We typically use the Qiagen DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (69504) because it generally yields DNA of suitable quantity and quality for coral amplicon sequencing [1]. However, recent experimental data suggest that this kit may preferentially recover coral host DNA relative to Symbiodiniaceae and bacterial DNA (data in preparation). While this may be acceptable for comparative analyses across samples processed with the same extraction method, it may affect estimates of bacterial and Symbiodiniaceae diversity and relative abundance. For bacterial 16S and Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 amplicon surveys, we therefore recommend considering DNA isolation protocols with more balanced recovery across holobiont compartments, such as the Qiagen DNeasy Plant Pro Kit (69204). For multi-marker profiling, the same DNA extracts should be used across all amplicon assays to maintain comparability.

- ITS2 amplicon primers: SYM_VAR_5.8S2 and SYM_VAR_REV

Note: These primers perform superior to other Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 primers and show high amplification specificity and high sensitivity towards Symbiodiniaceae with very little to no cross-amplification of other species/genera/taxa [4,5]; the ITS2 amplicon produced with these primers is also downstream-compatible with SymPortal analysis [6].

Forward primer (SYM_VAR_5.8S2): 5'-GAA TTG CAG AAC TCC GTG AAC C-3'

Reverse primer (SYM_VAR_REV): 5'-CGG GTT CWC TTG TYT GAC TTC ATG C-3'

- primer barcoding

Note: We use 8 barcoded forward primers and 12 barcoded reverse primers, generating 96 unique forward/reverse barcode combinations for unambiguous sample identification. Primer details and the 96-well plate layout are provided below.

Name	Sequence (5'-3'; barcode in bold)
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 1	AACGTGAT GAATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 2	AAACATCGG AATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 3	CATCAAGT GAATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 4	CGCTGATC GAATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 5	ACGTATCAG AATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 6	ACTATGCAG AATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 7	CAGCGTTAG AATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR 5.8S FOR 8	CATACCAAG AATTGCAGAACTCCGTGAACC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 1	GCTAACGAC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 2	GCTCGGTAC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 3	TATCAGCAC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 4	TCCGTCTAC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 5	AATGTTGCC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 6	ACACGACCC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 7	GATGAATCC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
ITS2 SYM VAR REV 8	GCCAAGACC GGGTTWCCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC

ITS2 SYM VAR REV 9
 ITS2 SYM VAR REV 10
 ITS2 SYM VAR REV 11
 ITS2 SYM VAR REV 12

TGGTGGTACGGGTTWCWCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
TTCACGCACGGGTTWCWCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
CGACTGGACGGGTTWCWCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC
CGCATACACGGGTTWCWCTTGTYTGACTTCATGC

		R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
F1	A	F1 + R1	F1 + R2	F1 + R3	F1 + R4	F1 + R5	F1 + R6	F1 + R7	F1 + R8	F1 + R9	F1 + R10	F1 + R11	F1 + R12
F2	B	F2 + R1	F2 + R2	F2 + R3	F2 + R4	F2 + R5	F2 + R6	F2 + R7	F2 + R8	F2 + R9	F2 + R10	F2 + R11	F2 + R12
F3	C	F3 + R1	F3 + R2	F3 + R3	F3 + R4	F3 + R5	F3 + R6	F3 + R7	F3 + R8	F3 + R9	F3 + R10	F3 + R11	F3 + R12
F4	D	F4 + R1	F4 + R2	F4 + R3	F4 + R4	F4 + R5	F4 + R6	F4 + R7	F4 + R8	F4 + R9	F4 + R10	F4 + R11	F4 + R12
F5	E	F5 + R1	F5 + R2	F5 + R3	F5 + R4	F5 + R5	F5 + R6	F5 + R7	F5 + R8	F5 + R9	F5 + R10	F5 + R11	F5 + R12
F6	F	F6 + R1	F6 + R2	F6 + R3	F6 + R4	F6 + R5	F6 + R6	F6 + R7	F6 + R8	F6 + R9	F6 + R10	F6 + R11	F6 + R12
F7	G	F7 + R1	F7 + R2	F7 + R3	F7 + R4	F7 + R5	F7 + R6	F7 + R7	F7 + R8	F7 + R9	F7 + R10	F7 + R11	F7 + R12
F8	H	F8 + R1	F8 + R2	F8 + R3	F8 + R4	F8 + R5	F8 + R6	F8 + R7	F8 + R8	F8 + R9	F8 + R10	F8 + R11	F8 + R12

- perform 1 PCR per sample with 5-20 ng DNA input (works with as little as 1-2 ng DNA input)

Note: We commonly use 1 µL of the extracted DNA; in our experience, less DNA works better as you also increase the amount of putative inhibitors with higher DNA amounts (i.e., sample volumes); consider using a DNA cleanup kit if amplification is an issue.

- Prepare the master mix according to the number of samples. Include a 5–10% excess volume to account for pipetting loss (prepare 100–105 reactions for 96-well plate).

Reagent	1 reaction [µL] / per well
Qiagen Multiplex PCR master mix (Qmix)	5
Nuclease free water	3
MasterMix volume	8
Forward & Reverse Primer [10 µM]; sample-specific	1
DNA template; sample-specific	1
Total volume (PCR reaction)	10

PCR thermocycler program:
 95°C 15 mins (hot start)
 95° C 30 secs |
 56°C 30 secs | 30 cycles
 72°C 30 secs |
 72°C 10 mins
 hold at 12°C

Note: We commonly use 30 PCR cycles as a trade-off between sufficient amplification and preservation of relative abundance information. Increasing the number of cycles may improve product yield, but can also increase PCR bias and distort relative abundance ratios; use 35 cycles in case of weak PCR amplification

Note: We commonly use a hold temperature of 12°C; 4°C is shortens the lifetime of thermal cyclers and costs excessive energy

- Confirm successful PCR amplification by running 2 µL PCR product (+2 µL water + 1 µl 6X loading dye) on a gel

Note: Check for distinct, sharp bands; commonly, band intensity varies across samples; always run a 1kb ladder and ideally positive/negative PCR control

Sample-barcoding PCR protocol - Coral ITS2 amplicon survey

Objective: Barcoded primers and PCR amplification conditions for DNA extracted from coral samples. Samples will be individually amplified and then pooled prior to sequencing submission.

- use your DNA extraction method of choice

Note: We typically use the Qiagen DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (69504) because it generally yields DNA of suitable quantity and quality for coral amplicon sequencing [1]. However, recent experimental data suggest that this kit may preferentially isolate coral host DNA relative to Symbiodiniaceae and bacterial DNA (data in preparation). This bias can be advantageous for coral ITS2 amplicon surveys, where host DNA is the target. However, if bacterial 16S and Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 amplicon surveys are planned, we recommend using an alternative DNA isolation protocol that provides more balanced recovery across holobiont compartments. Importantly, the same DNA extracts should be used across all amplicon assays to ensure comparability among marker systems. Suitable alternatives include the Qiagen DNeasy Plant Pro Kit (69204).

- ITS2 amplicon primers: coral_ITS2_host_for and coral_ITS2_host_rev

Note: The ITS2 primer set presented here [7] was developed based on available coral ITS2 primer pairs [8–10]. The coral_ITS2_host_for/coral_ITS2_host_rev primer pair provides very high amplification recovery across coral DNA samples but may also amplify sponges and other non-scleractinian taxa. It is therefore well suited for coral tissue DNA, where coral host template DNA is expected to dominate. In contrast, applications such as eDNA-based coral ITS2 amplification require primers with greater target specificity and reduced non-target amplification [7].

Forward primer (coral_ITS2_host_for): 5'-GAD TCT TTG AAC GCA AAT GGC-3'
Reverse primer (coral_ITS2_host_rev): 5'-TCG CCG TTA CTR RGG GAA TC -3'

- primer barcoding

Note: We use 8 barcoded forward primers and 12 barcoded reverse primers, generating 96 unique forward/reverse barcode combinations for unambiguous sample identification. Primer details and the 96-well plate layout are provided below.

Name	Sequence (5'-3'; barcode in bold)
ITS2 coral FOR 1	AACGTGAT GADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 2	AAACATCGG ADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 3	CATCAAGT GADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 4	CGCTGATC GADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 5	ACGTATCAG ADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 6	ACTATGCAG ADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 7	CAGCGTTA GADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral FOR 8	CATACCAAG ADTCTTTGAACGCAAATGGC
ITS2 coral REV 1	GCTAACGAT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC
ITS2 coral REV 2	GCTCGGTAT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC
ITS2 coral REV 3	TATCAGCAT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC
ITS2 coral REV 4	TCCGTCTAT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC
ITS2 coral REV 5	AATGTTGCT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC
ITS2 coral REV 6	ACACGACCT CGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC

ITS2 coral REV 7 **GATGAATCTCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**
 ITS2 coral REV 8 **GCCAAGACTCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**
 ITS2 coral REV 9 **TGGTGGTATCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**
 ITS2 coral REV 10 **TTCACGCATCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**
 ITS2 coral REV 11 **CGACTGGATCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**
 ITS2 coral REV 12 **CGCATACATCGCCGTTACTRRGGGAATC**

		R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
F1	A	F1 + R1	F1 + R2	F1 + R3	F1 + R4	F1 + R5	F1 + R6	F1 + R7	F1 + R8	F1 + R9	F1 + R10	F1 + R11	F1 + R12
F2	B	F2 + R1	F2 + R2	F2 + R3	F2 + R4	F2 + R5	F2 + R6	F2 + R7	F2 + R8	F2 + R9	F2 + R10	F2 + R11	F2 + R12
F3	C	F3 + R1	F3 + R2	F3 + R3	F3 + R4	F3 + R5	F3 + R6	F3 + R7	F3 + R8	F3 + R9	F3 + R10	F3 + R11	F3 + R12
F4	D	F4 + R1	F4 + R2	F4 + R3	F4 + R4	F4 + R5	F4 + R6	F4 + R7	F4 + R8	F4 + R9	F4 + R10	F4 + R11	F4 + R12
F5	E	F5 + R1	F5 + R2	F5 + R3	F5 + R4	F5 + R5	F5 + R6	F5 + R7	F5 + R8	F5 + R9	F5 + R10	F5 + R11	F5 + R12
F6	F	F6 + R1	F6 + R2	F6 + R3	F6 + R4	F6 + R5	F6 + R6	F6 + R7	F6 + R8	F6 + R9	F6 + R10	F6 + R11	F6 + R12
F7	G	F7 + R1	F7 + R2	F7 + R3	F7 + R4	F7 + R5	F7 + R6	F7 + R7	F7 + R8	F7 + R9	F7 + R10	F7 + R11	F7 + R12
F8	H	F8 + R1	F8 + R2	F8 + R3	F8 + R4	F8 + R5	F8 + R6	F8 + R7	F8 + R8	F8 + R9	F8 + R10	F8 + R11	F8 + R12

- perform 1 PCR per sample with 5-20 ng DNA input (works with as little as 1-2 ng DNA input)

Note: We commonly use 1 µL of the extracted DNA; in our experience, less DNA works better as you also increase the amount of putative inhibitors with higher DNA amounts (i.e., sample volumes); consider using a DNA cleanup kit if amplification is an issue.

- Prepare the master mix according to the number of samples. Include a 5–10% excess volume to account for pipetting loss (prepare 100–105 reactions for 96-well plate).

Reagent	1 reaction [µL] / per well
Qiagen Multiplex PCR master mix (Qmix)	5
Nuclease free water	3
MasterMix volume	8
Forward & Reverse Primer [10 µM]; sample-specific	1
DNA template; sample-specific	1
Total volume (PCR reaction)	10

PCR thermocycler program:
 95°C 15 mins (hot start)
 95°C 30 secs |
 52°C 30 secs | 30 cycles
 72°C 30 secs |
 72°C 10 mins
 hold at 12°C

Note: We commonly use 30 PCR cycles as a trade-off between sufficient amplification and preservation of relative abundance information. Increasing the number of cycles may improve product yield, but can also increase PCR bias and distort relative abundance ratios; use 35 cycles in case of weak PCR amplification

Note: We commonly use a hold temperature of 12°C; 4°C is shortens the lifetime of thermal cyclers and costs excessive energy

- Confirm successful PCR amplification by running 2 µL PCR product (+3 µL water + 1 µl 6X loading dye) on a gel

Note: Check for distinct, sharp bands; commonly, band intensity varies across samples; always run a 1kb ladder and ideally positive/negative PCR control

PCR cleanup using AMPure XP Beads in 96 well plate format

Objective: This step uses AMPure XP magnetic beads ([A63880](#)) to purify PCR products and normalize amplicon yield across samples before pooling. The cleanup removes residual primers, primer dimers, nucleotides, enzymes, salts, and other small reaction components, while retaining amplicons in the expected size range. Bead-based normalization helps ensure that each sample contributes an approximately equal number of DNA molecules to the pooled sequencing library, thereby improving library quality, reducing downstream interference, and supporting balanced sample representation during sequencing.

- read the full protocol here: <https://www.beckman.de/reagents/genomic/cleanup-and-size-selection/pcr/ampure-xp-protocol>
- the protocol is the same for all amplicons

Binding Step

- Shake the AMPure XP bottle to resuspend any magnetic particles that may have settled. The color of the mixture should appear homogenous after mixing
- Add the AMPure XP reagent according to the sample reaction volume shown in the table (volume of AMPure XP per reaction = 1.8 x reaction volume):

PCR reaction volume (µL)	AMPure XP volume (µL)
8	15
10	18
20	36
50	90
100	180

- Mix reagent and sample thoroughly by pipette-mixing 10 times.
- Let the mixed samples incubate for 5 minutes at room temperature for maximum recovery.
- Place the reaction plate onto the 96-well magnet plate (e.g., Alpaqua, catalyst 96, [A000550](#)) for 2 minutes to separate beads from the solution.

Note: Wait for the solution to clear before proceeding to the next step.

- Aspirate the cleared solution from the reaction plate and discard. Leave 5 µL of supernatant behind, otherwise beads are drawn out with the supernatant.

Note: Do not disturb the ring of separated magnetic beads.

Washing Step

- Add 200 µL of freshly prepared 70% ethanol to each well while the plate remains on the magnetic stand. Incubate for 30 seconds at room temperature, then carefully aspirate and discard the ethanol without disturbing the beads.
- Repeat the ethanol wash once, for a total of two washes.

Note: The beads are not drawn out easily when in alcohol, so it is not necessary to leave any supernatant behind. Do not overdry as this will affect elution efficiency

Elution Step

- Remove the reaction plate from the magnet plate and add 40 μL of elution buffer to each well of the reaction plate and pipette mix 10 times. Incubate for 2 minutes.

Note: The liquid level will be high enough to contact the magnetic beads at a 40 μL elution volume. A greater volume of elution buffer can be used, but using less than 40 μL will require extra mixing (to ensure the liquid comes into contact with the beads), and may not be sufficient to elute the entire PCR product.

- Place the reaction plate onto the 96-well magnet plate for 1 minute to separate beads from the solution.
- Transfer the eluate to a new plate.
- Store the eluted DNA at 4°C (short-term storage) or -20°C (long-term storage)

Note: Bead carryover is not a cause for concern. The samples can be stored in the freezer with beads and the beads are inert in downstream enzymatic reactions. If bead carryover must be limited for any reason, 2 μL – 5 μL of eluate can be left behind in the original plate.

Note: The expected DNA concentration is about 1–5 ng/ μL per sample/well.

Figure 1. Gel electrophoresis of PCR amplicon products before (top) and after (bottom) AMPure XP bead-based cleanup. Left: 16S amplicon PCRs; right: Symbiodiniaceae ITS2 PCRs.

Pool library, adjust pool concentration, and final gel-based cleanup

- Pool 96 samples per sequencing library by combining an equal volume (20 μ L) from each cleaned PCR product into a 2 mL reaction tube

Note: We typically pool 20 μ L from each sample (leaving 20 μ L as backup). For 96 samples, this results in a total pooled volume of approximately 1.9 mL; therefore, a 2 mL reaction tube is required.

- Concentrate the pooled library using a SpeedVac to a final volume of approximately 50-100 μ L to increase DNA concentration and obtain a volume suitable for gel-based cleanup.
- Run the total volume of the pooled sample on an agarose gel to remove residual PCR side products and any carried-over magnetic beads.

Note: Magnetic beads carried over from the PCR cleanup step are generally not expected to interfere with downstream processing. During gel electrophoresis, residual beads remain trapped in the gel wells, thereby preventing their transfer to the final pooled library.

- Place the gel on a UV transilluminator, excise the amplicon band using a sterile scalpel, and transfer the gel fragment to a 2 mL reaction tube.
- Purify the excised amplicon band using the QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (cat. nr. 28704) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Use an elution volume of 30 μ L.
- Confirm successful gel extraction by running 2 μ L of the purified pooled library on a gel.
- Assess DNA concentration of the pooled library. The pooled library should be ≥ 200 ng DNA at a minimum concentration of 10 ng/ μ L.
- Submit the pooled, gel-purified, and concentrated amplicon library for sequencing.

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